

obtaining the magnetic and electronic spectral data of the complexes.

References

1. G. S. YAMADA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 4, 415.
2. T. N. WALTERS and P. E. WRIGHT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 359.
3. O. B. WEST "New Pathways in Inorg. Chem", 1968, 303.
4. G. R. BRUBAKER, C. J. LATTI and C. DOLORES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 268.
5. V. I. MINKIN, O. A. OSIPOV, V. A. KOGAN, R. R. SHAGIDUEHEIMA, R. L. TERENTEEV and O. A. RAEVSKII, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 38, 938.
6. M. O. COHEN and S. FLAVIAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 321.
7. K. VENO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 998.
8. A. E. MARTELL, R. L. BELFORD and M. COLVIN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 5, 170.
9. A. S. EGOROV, V. A. KOGAN, O. A. OSIPOV and I. G. STRIZHKOVA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 20, 365.
10. R. N. PRASAD and J. P. TANDON, *J. Less Common Metals*, 1974, 37, 141.
11. S. K. AGARWAL and J. P. TANDON, *Syn. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1974, 4, 387.
12. S. F. A. KETTLE and A. J. P. PIOLE, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1423.

Structural Studies on Palladium(II) and Cobalt(III) Complexes of Isonitroso- β -diketones

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ISONITROSOBENZOYLACETONE (HINBA) and isonitrosodibenzoylmethane (HINDBM) have been used in this laboratory for the spectrophotometric determination of iron, palladium and ruthenium¹⁻³. The present communication deals with the preparation and structural characterization of solid complexes of Pd(II) and Co(III) with HINBA and HINDBM.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. HINBA and HINDBM were prepared by the reported methods⁴. Palladium complexes were prepared by mixing acidic solution of PdCl₂ and alcoholic solution of ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. On dropwise addition of sodium acetate orange-red complexes precipitates out. The precipitate was digested on a hot plate for 20-30 min, filtered, washed with water, ethanol and finally dried

under vacuum. Cobalt(III) complexes were prepared by mixing aqueous solution of CoCl₂ and alcoholic solution of ligand in 1:3 molar ratio and then added sodium hydroxide solution to precipitate complexes. Rest procedure is followed as above.

Metal was estimated by standard methods and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made by Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra were recorded on NaCl(KBr) prism using Perkin-Elmer (221) Spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded using Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer and PMR were recorded in CDCl₃ using varian spectrometers with TMS as the standard. The molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopy method. All the relevant analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The orange-red Pd(INBA)₂ and Pd(INDBM)₂ decompose at 150° and 190° respectively. The yellow-orange Co(INBA)₃ and Co(INDBM)₃ decompose at 210° and 195° respectively. 1:2 and 1:3 stoichiometry for palladium and cobalt complexes respectively were confirmed by elemental analysis and molecular weight determinations. All the complexes are soluble in solvents such as methanol, chloroform, benzene, acetone and ethylacetate. All solid complexes were found to be diamagnetic. This reveals that the palladium complexes must be planar in structure whereas cobalt complexes are octahedral involving d³SP³ hybridization. Bivalent cobalt gets oxidized to trivalent cobalt during complexation with isonitroso compounds.

The PMR spectrum of the HINBA and HINDBM in CDCl₃ show signals at 1.4 and 1.5 τ (with respect to TMS) respectively, which is assigned to the =NOH groups. HINBA exhibits methyl signals at 7.55 τ and phenyl signals at 2.18-2.62 τ . HINDBM exhibits bands at 1.88-2.64 τ . These bands are attributed to proton resonance signals from C₆H₅ groups. The integration of peak areas reveal that the ratio of the area under the peak at 1.5 τ to that under the peak at 1.88-2.64 τ approximates to ten. The metal complexes of both the ligands do not show any signal due to the =NOH group which indicates the replacement of the oxime proton by the metal during complexation.

The IR bands and their characteristic assignment are based on the study of the free ligands and their complexes. The strong and broad band around 3370-3300 cm⁻¹ in ligands is attributed to hydrogen bonded -OH stretching frequency of the oxime group. The disappearance of this band in metal complexes suggests the replacement of the hydrogen of the oxime group by metal on complexation. This observation is in agreement with the results of PMR studies. One strong band at 1660-1650 cm⁻¹ in metal complexes is assigned to C=O of aromatic ketone which indicates that the complexes are symmetric in nature. The weak band at 1620 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is assigned to C=N

TABLE I—PMR, UV AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF PALLADIUM AND COBALTC COMPLEXES

Complex	Elemental analysis								PMR signals in τ with respect to TMS	Electronic absorption bands in kK (ϵ)	
	Calculated				Found					Methanol	Chloroform
	C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M			
HINBA	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.4, 2.18-2.62, 7.55	39.2	39.2
HINDBM	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.5, 1.88-2.64, —	39.0	39.4
Pd(INBA) ₂	49.3	3.3	5.7	21.8	48.2	3.8	5.9	21.0	—, 2.34-2.70, 7.55	40.3(4999), 25.6(4700)	40.3(1693), 24.7(3725)
Co(INBA) ₂	57.2	3.8	6.6	9.34	56.9	3.9	6.6	9.36	—, 2.00-2.60, 7.50	40.7(15630), 35.7(13110), 27.8(5771)	27.8(18870)
Pd(INDBM) ₂	59.0	3.3	4.6	17.4	60.0	3.5	4.9	17.4	—, 2.20-2.80, —	39.4(6542), 25.0(3763)	39.4(24770), 24.3(25450)
Co(INDBM) ₂	66.2	3.7	5.1	7.2	65.8	3.6	4.9	7.4	—, 1.80-2.80, —	—	27.8(41190)

stretching. The bands at 1595 and 1575 cm^{-1} in the complexes are attributed to perturbed C=O and or C=N stretching. The bands at 1575 cm^{-1} may also be assigned to C=C stretching frequency. The ν_{NO} observed in the region 1240–1225 cm^{-1} indicates that the coordination of the metal has taken through nitrogen of the oxime group. The bands at 612 and 600 cm^{-1} observed in Pd(INDBM)₂ and Co(INDBM)₂ complexes may be assigned to M-N vibration mode.

The electronic spectrum of HINBA and HINDBM in methanol and chloroform solution show one absorption band at 39.0–39.4 kK which may be assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition in the ligand. The intensity of this band increases in Pd(INBA)₂ (40.3 kK, $\epsilon=4999$ in CH_3OH ; 40.3 kK, $\epsilon=1693$ in CHCl_3), and Pd(INDBM)₂ (39.4 kK, $\epsilon=6542$ in CH_3OH ; 39.4 kK, $\epsilon=24770$ in CHCl_3) complexes. Both Pd(INBA)₂ and Pd(INDBM)₂ in methanol show one more absorption band at 25.6 kK and 25.0 kK respectively which may be assigned to charge transfer transitions. In chloroform these band shift to 24.7 kK and 24.3 kK respectively. Co(INBA)₂ in methanol show three absorption bands. The bands at 40.7 kK ($\epsilon=15630$) and 35.7 kK ($\epsilon=13110$) may be attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition whereas the charge transfer transition appears at 27.8 kK ($\epsilon=571$). Co(INBA)₂ and Co(INDBM)₂ in chloroform show charge transfer bands at 27.8 kK.

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References

1. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Analyst*, 1979, 140, 160.
2. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.* 1979, 295, 412.
3. B. J. DESAI and V. M. SHINDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1979, 298, 158.
4. BEILSTEIN, *Handbuch Der organische Chemie*, Band VII, 864, 1409.

Potentiometric Studies of Complex Formation of Some Trivalent Rare Earths with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-2-Iminopyridine**

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IN continuation to our earlier studies on Schiff-base ligands and their metal complexes^{1,2}, we report in the present communication our potentiometric studies of the proton-ligand stability constants of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2-iminopyridine and its formation of 1:1 complexes with Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III) and Gd(III).

All chemicals and reagents used in the study were either of A.R. grade or purified before use.

The Schiff-base ligand was prepared by an analogous method as described in our earlier paper². The purity of the ligand was checked by elemental analysis and melting point determination.

Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution³ and double distilled water were used. Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates and were estimated by EDTA method⁴. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1M HClO_4 to avoid metal hydrolysis.

A digital pH-meter of Electronics Corporation of India, model No. pH-5651 (accuracy ± 0.01 unit) with combined glass electrode assembly was used for the present study. All computation works were done in programmable calculator (EC 62 p) of Electronics Corporation of India.

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